

Ecommerce website for gen Z users

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Abstract - This project focuses on creating an e-commerce website for Gen Z users. Gen Z is the generation born between 1995 and 2010, and they are the first generation to grow up with the internet. As such, they have a different set of expectations when it comes to shopping online. This project aims to create an e-commerce website that is tailored to the needs and preferences of Gen Z users. This website will feature a modern design, intuitive navigation, and a variety of features to make shopping easier and more enjoyable for Gen Z users. Additionally, this website will incorporate various social media platforms to create an engaging and interactive shopping experience. By creating an e-commerce website that is designed specifically for Gen Z users, this project will help bridge the gap between traditional online shopping and the needs of this new generation of shoppers.

Keywords - E-commerce website; Gen-Z; Social Media; Personalized product; Online shopping

1.0 Introduction

The E-commerce website for genZ users project is an initiative to create a web-based platform that caters to the needs of Gen Z users. It is designed to provide an engaging and user-friendly shopping experience for this demographic. The website will include features such as personalized product recommendations, an interactive chatbot, and an intuitive search engine. It will also provide a secure payment gateway and a rewards program to reward customers for their loyalty. The project will also focus on providing an enjoyable and safe shopping experience for users, with a focus on data privacy and security.

2.0 System Design

2.1 ER Diagram of the Database

2.2 UML Diagram

2.3 Data Flow Diagram

User can add different items in th cart as well as can buy any item directly using buy now option.

3.5 Customer Support:

In case of any problem, a user can get support through our dedicated customer care numbers or can chat with a representative but at the first step they have to interact with the chatbot if the chatbot can't solve the issue then a support ticket will be generated for the user.

4.0 Feature list:

- 1) The very simple and easy onboarding process for both the seller and the customer.
- 1) A very clean interface will ensure easy navigation in the system which will uplift the user's experience.
- 1) A very effective and precise search option for the users to find what they want.
- 1) Prebuilt filters (price, rating, brands, etc).
- 1) Users can rate and review an item only after buying.
- 1) The interface will be very snappy.
- 1) A customer can directly connect with the seller.
- 1) Brands can also do a campaign in our app or on our website for a fixed cost.
- 1) 0 upfront cost for the sellers, pay if and only if your product gets sold.
- 1) All the user data will be stored over the blockchain for better security.
- 1) The suggested products will be based on user data.
- 1) Users will also be rewarded with gift cards and many more.
- 1) An inventory management system for the sellers for their better inventory management.

5.0 Conclusion:

We will be able to create an engaging, user-friendly website that provided an easy and enjoyable shopping experience for our target audience.

By using the latest technologies and trends to ensure that our website will be up-to-date and secure.

Our website will also be aesthetically pleasing, allowing our users to easily find what they were looking for.

Overall, our website will be able in providing a positive shopping experience for our genZ users.

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